

Dihydroisocoumarins: Part XII. The Preparation and Reduction of Methyl 2-carboxy-5-methoxyphenylacetate

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A convenient route to dihydroisocoumarins has been reported earlier^{1,2}. Based on the same reaction sequences, methyl 2-carboxy-5-methoxyphenylacetate, prepared by methanolysis of 5-methoxyhomophthalic anhydride³, was reduced with lithium borohydride to afford 3,4-dihydro-6-methoxyisocoumarin.

EXPERIMENTAL

Methyl 2-Carboxy-5-methoxyphenylacetate. A suspension of 5-methoxy-homophthalic anhydride³ (5 g.) in absolute methanol (30 ml.) was refluxed on water bath for 2 hr. The solid slowly dissolved and as the reaction proceeded yellow flakes appeared. Evaporation of the solvent left a crystalline residue which when crystallised from ethyl acetate-light petroleum (b.p. 60–80°) afforded pure *methyl 2-carboxy-5-methoxyphenylacetate* as needles (5.1 g., 92.7%), m.p. 157–58°. (Found: C, 58.1; H, 5.6. C₁₁H₁₂O₅ requires: C, 58.9; H, 5.3%).

3,4-Dihydro-6-methoxyisocoumarin. LiBH₄ (0.5 g.) was added to a solution of the foregoing half-ester (2.5 g.) in dry THF (50 ml.) and the reaction mixture was heated under gentle reflux for 5 hr. Next day, the solvent was distilled off, and the complex decomposed by careful addition of ice-cold water, followed by 2N-H₂SO₄, until a clear solution was obtained. It was extracted with chloroform (3 × 25 ml.) and the extract washed repeatedly with aq. NaHCO₃ followed by water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Evaporation of the solvent left a yellow gum, the benzene solution of which was chromatographed through a column of Brockmann's alumina, using the same solvent as the eluent. Evaporation of the solvent furnished a crystalline residue (1.9 g.) which was recrystallised from ethyl acetate-light petroleum (b.p. 40–60°) to yield, 3,4-dihydro-6-methoxyisocoumarin as colourless fine needles (1.5 g.; 80%), m.p. 71–2°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen (m.p. 70°) prepared earlier⁴ by a different route.

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